

THOT THEORY OF TONE

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Kugama. Analytical report on the tonal system

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On the basis of the Version 8b of the Questionnaire

This report is based on Lora Litvinova's analysis of the Kugama tonal system (Litvinova 2023).

1. General information

1.1. Language names

The name *Kugama* (ISO 639-3: kow; Glottocode: kuga1239) is an exonym, while *ɲáá 'wàṃ* and *ɲáá 'wàā* are endonyms.

1.2. Language affiliation

Kugama is traditionally classified within the Adamawa language family of Niger-Congo (Eberhard et al. 2023). However, in Glottolog 5.0, the Admawa language family is no longer recognized, and Kugama is currently placed within the Cameroun-Ubangian language family under the Central Adamawa branch.

Kugama is spoken in the Adamawa State of Nigeria.

1.3. Sociolinguistic situation

According to Ethnologue (Eberhard et al. 2023), in 1995 Kugama was spoken by 5000 speakers.

Kugama people live in an area where many other languages are spoken. Due to the widespread multilingualism in the region, the Kugama use Hausa as a lingua franca when communicating with other groups.

No dialectological study of Kugama has been carried out. In this report some cases of interspeaker variations in the application of tonal rules will be mentioned.

2. Segmental phonology

2.1. Phonemic inventory

2.1.1. Vowels

Kugama 24 vowel phonemes contrast in length and nasality. Oral short and long vowels distinguish four degrees of vowel height, see Table 1.

Table 1. Kugama short and long oral vowels

i i:		u u:
e e:		o o:
ɛ ɛ:		ɔ ɔ:
a a:		

Nasal short and long vowels distinguish three degrees of vowel height, see Table 2.

Table 2. Kugama short and long nasal vowels

ĩ ĩ:		ũ ũ:
ɛ̃ ɛ̃:		ɔ̃ ɔ̃:
ã ã:		

Long vowels are represented in writing by doubling the vowel, e.g. *aa*. Nasal vowels are indicated with a tilde under the letter (*ã* or *ãã*) in order not to pile up tone and nasality markings.

Phonemic status of long vowel phonemes can be supported by the following:

- Syllables containing long vowels, VV and CVV, behave in the same way as the other heavy syllables, VC and CVC, they are opposed to light syllables, V and CV. For instance, the choice of an allomorph of the perfective enclitic =*tí*/=*rí* depends on the

weight of the preceding syllable: =*tí* comes after a light syllable (V or CV), while =*rí* appears after a heavy syllable (VV, CVV, VC or CVC), e.g. *sáá*=*rí* (draw=PFV) and *sám*=*rí* (send=PFV), but *sá*=*tí* (speak=PFV).

- Syllables with long vowel phonemes commonly occur in the beginning of a root, e.g. *dòòrì* ‘star’, *léérē* ‘flute’.

2.1.2. Consonants

Kugama has 25 consonant phonemes, see Table 3. The consonant inventory includes the labial-velar stops /kp/ and /gb/ and the implosives /ɓ/ and /ɗ/. The inventory is represented according to the IPA conventions, except for five phonemes: /z/, /r/, /y/, /kp/ and /gb/. Their IPA representations are given in square brackets in Table 3.

Table 3. Consonant inventory of Kugama

	Labial		Labio-dental	Alveolar		Palatal	Velar		Glottal	Labial-velar	
Plosive	p	b		t	d		k	g	ʔ	kp [kp̩]	gb [gb̩]
Implosive		ɓ			ɗ						
Nasal	m			n		ɲ	ŋ			w	
Fricative			f	v	s				h		
Affricate						z [dz̩]					
Tap					r [r]						
Approximant					l	y [j]				w	

2.2. Prosodic units

2.2.1. Syllable and mora

Kugama has light syllable types V, CV and heavy syllable types VV, CVV, VC, and CVC. The inventory of consonants in coda position is generally limited to the nasals /m/ and /ŋ/, the approximant /y/, and the glottal stop /ʔ/. Roots (referred to as stems in Litvinova 2023) in Kugama are predominantly monosyllabic and disyllabic. A root is an underived and uninflected word form, e.g. *á* ‘go’, *úy* ‘head’, *gūnā* ‘rattles’, *bám* ‘become old’.

A tone-bearing unit (TBU) in Kugama is a mora. A heavy syllable can carry a sequence of two tonemes, as in the Definite marker =*rêʔ* and the noun *tèé* ‘chicken’. In less careful speech,

monosyllabic nouns can optionally be pronounced with short vowels, as in *fǎà* ~ *fǎ* ‘small, young one’.

2.2.2. Word form

A prosodic word in Kugama can be monosyllabic or polysyllabic. It can consist of a root, e.g. *sǎm̄* ‘work’, or a root with enclitics, e.g. *sǎm̄rí* ‘work of (someone)’ (*sǎm̄* ‘work’ + =^L GEN + =rí POSS + =^L GEN + ...).

Most Kugama noun roots are monosyllabic or disyllabic. Nouns with more than two syllables are mostly borrowings or historically complex forms. Monosyllabic noun roots are usually represented by heavy syllables, CVV or CVC. Underived Kugama verb roots are also monosyllabic or disyllabic. A monosyllabic verb and the first syllable of a disyllabic verb can take one of the following shapes: V, CV, VV, CVV, VC, or CVC. The second syllable of a disyllabic verb is always light.

The word-initial syllable is characterized by prosodic prominence. In a prominent syllable, almost all consonants, vowels and syllable types can occur, while only a subset of consonants, vowels and syllable types is found in the prosodically weak position. More information on prosodic prominence is provided in Section 5.3.

3. Tonal inventory

3.1. Character of tonal system

Kugama has a level-tone system including high, mid and low levels.

3.2. Inventory of tonemes

Kugama has two level tonemes: High (H) and Low (L). In addition, Kugama has a M tone which is analyzed as a default tone on toneless morae and syllables, see Section 4.3. It is indicated in the phonetic transcription (given without brackets). (Morpho)phonological transcription is given between slashes.

The following criteria for determining the tonemic status of H can be provided:

- The Activity Criterion: a H tone can spread (Section 6.1.3, Section 6.1.4).

The following criteria for determining the tonemic status of L can be provided:

- The Tonal Morpheme Criterion: a L tone can be a tonal grammatical morpheme, viz. the Genitive =^L and the Resultative =^L (Section 7).
- The Activity Criterion: a L tone can spread (Section 6.1.5).

- The Floating Criterion: a L tone can float (Section 3.3).

Contour tones are sequences of level tonemes:

- The Non-Compositionality Criterion is not applied here, because Kugama does not have a tonal contour realized on one TBU and composed of tonal levels, which are not tonemes.

3.3. Floating tones

Kugama has floating L tones. They can be part of a lexical tonal melody, e.g. /dʒéɛkɛ^L/ ‘house’ in (1). They also appear as exponents of grammatical morphemes: the Genitive marker =^L and the Resultative marker =^L, see Section 7 for more details.

- (1) dʒéɛkɛ ʼbíní
 /dʒéɛkɛ^L bíní^L/
 house one
 ‘one house’

A floating L is always preceded by H in surface realization and is commonly expressed through a downstep of the following tone, as in (2) - (4).

- (2) báá ʼnáákí
 /báa=^L náaki/
 stomach = GEN cow
 ‘stomach of the cow’

- (3) nós ʼdĩŋsì
 /nós=^L dĩŋsì/
 fruit = GEN tree
 ‘fruit of the tree’

- (4) úú ʼwēm
 /úu=^L wem/
 head = GEN person
 ‘head of the person’

A tonal morpheme expressed by a floating L tone can appear after a segment with any linked toneme (H or L), as well as after a toneless segment. When a floating L comes after a linked L or after another floating L, it is deleted, as in (5) and (6).

3.4.2. Downstep

Downstep is caused by a floating L tone. This L tone can be lexical, as in *dàá* /*dàá*^L/ ‘sheep’, or it can be an exponent of a tonal morpheme, see (10).

- (10) tɛ́ɛ́ ʼbàà ~ tɛ́ɛ́ ʼbàā
/tɛ́ɛ́ =^L bàa/
chicken = GEN flock
‘chicken of the flock’

Any tone, H, L or default M, can be downstepped.

- (11) báá ʼnáákī
/báá =^L náaki/
stomach = GEN cow
‘stomach of the cow’
- (12) jáá ʼwàm̄ ~ jáá ʼwām̄
/jáá =^L wàm/
mouth = GEN Kugama
‘Kugama language’
- (13) kùm ʼwēm̄
/kùm =^L wem/
bone = GEN person
‘skeleton’

When a noun phrase contains more than one floating L tone, the first downstep is obligatory, and the subsequent ones are optional: it is attested in (14), but it can be omitted in less careful speech (15). Even if there is no downstep, the second floating L tone is still postulated, as it triggers the spreading of the preceding H tone onto the following toneless mora, as in (15) with the noun *nɔ́ɔ* ‘eye’.

- (14) vísí ʼnáá ʼváā
/vísí =^L náá =^L váa/
finger = GEN hand = GEN child
‘finger of the child’ (lit.: ‘finger of the hand of the child’)

- (15) ɓìtɔ́ ʰnɔ́ɔ léȳ
 /ɓìtɔ́^L nɔ́ɔ =^L léȳ/
 SG.1PL.POSS eye = GEN fire
 ‘our gun’ (lit. our eye of fire)

It is not clear whether the second floating L tone lowers a subsequent L or M, as these tones are already lower than the preceding H, as in (16).

- (16) váá ʰbá yēy
 /váá =^L báa =^L yey/
 child = GEN inside = GEN wind
 ‘bastard’

3.5. Upstep

Downstep and downdrift are usually accompanied by an automatic raising of the H tone on a mora preceding a floating or linked L, as in (17) and (18).

- (17) ɲáá ʰwà̀m̄ ~ ɲáá ʰwà̀m̄
 /ɲáá =^L wà̀m̄/
 mouth = GEN Kugama
 ‘Kugama language’

- (18) sɔ̀ò gérē
 /sɔ̀ò gérē/
 female pig
 ‘sow’

3.6. Other suprasegmental features of tonemes apart from pitch

Other suprasegmental features of tonemes apart from pitch are not attested in Kugama.

4. Tonotactics

4.1. Tonal span

A tonal span can have a zero length (a floating L realized as a downstep), a mora, one or more syllables within a prosodic word.

The phrase *á* ‘Múúsá’ *‘It is Musa’* includes three tonal spans. [H a] [L] [H muusa], with a zero length tonal span for a floating L tone. A toneme can be realized on a mora, e.g. *fáà* ‘small,

young (sg.)’ [H fa] [L a], and on a syllable, e.g. *gérē* ‘pig’ [H gɛ] rɛ. In polysyllabic nouns, a L or H tonal span can be longer than one syllable, e.g. *gbíntélè* [H gbɪntɛ][L lɛ] ‘shortness’, *héntélè* [H hɛntɛ][L lɛ] ‘shallowness’, *sɛŋkélè* [H sɛŋkɛlɛ][L] ‘sharpness’, *kpìkpítírí* [L kpì][H kpitiri][L] ‘thickness’, *kpùkpóró* [L kpu][H kpɔrɔ][L] ‘bravery, intelligence’, *tɛŋtɛŋ* [H tɛŋtɛŋ][L] ‘cleanness, smart’, *bèntèlè* [L bɛntɛlɛ] ‘width’, *lèmlèm* [L lemlem] ‘slowly’.

A H tonal span can stretch across a morpheme boundary, but does not go beyond the limits of a prosodic word. This H tone spreading may be accompanied by L-tone delinking (19), see Section 6.1.4.

(19) mó 2SG + =è PRST + =yí QM → mó ɔ ‘yí [H mɔ.ɔ][L][H yi]

4.2. Combinations of tonemes

The most frequent tonal lexical patterns on nouns are H and L. They occur on monosyllabic and disyllabic nouns and include a final toneless mora or syllable that is phonetically realized with a default M tone, e.g. *béy* ‘stomach’, *bàā* ‘herd’, *yékí* ‘money’, *gàrē* ‘mountain’, *dòòrì* ‘star’. Tonemes can also be combined within a nominal form. These combinations are: L, LH, LH^L, H^L, HL, H^LH, LH^LH, e.g. *bèntèlè* ‘width’, *vùrè* ‘intestines’, *tɛ́ɛ́* ‘chicken’,¹ *kpàní* ‘chiefs’, *dàá* /dàá^L/ ‘sheep’, *gbiré* /gbiré^L/ ‘dwarf’, *dééké* /dééké^L/ ‘house’, *bíní* /bíní^L/ ‘one’, *dóò* ‘rope’, *tɛ́ntɛ́ŋ* /tɛ́ntɛ́ŋ^L/ ‘cleanness, smartness’, *bèpí* /bèpí^L/ ‘hare’, *kpùkpóró* /kpùkpóró^L/ ‘bravery, intelligence’, *bí’ná* /bí^L’ná/ ‘granary’ and *gàá’té* /gàá^L’té/ ‘morning’. Nouns whose H-tone span includes more than one syllable have a subsequent L toneme (either linked or floating, even though the floating L can be optional). Toneless segments do not commonly occur after polysyllabic H-toned spans within the same root. The final floating L in LH^L and H^L nouns is usually optional. However, it is most commonly retained in phrases where a noun is modified by a numeral. In this context, it triggers downstep in the tone of a numeral, as shown in (1).

There are also a number of nouns that are fully toneless and are realized with a default M tone, e.g. *dēē* ‘blood’, *wēnī* ‘people’ and *fōōrī* ‘poverty’. There are only several nouns with initial toneless syllable(s) and a final L-toned segment, e.g. *lūūmò* ‘market’, *gēlūbà* ‘camel’, *lēēsò* ‘beg’ and *tɔ̀y* ‘clay’. Some of them are borrowed from Fulfulde.

¹ A number of nouns have a LM realization. It is not always clear whether such a noun is L-toned with a default M tone or LH-toned with a final H phonetically realized as M because of downdrift. A test permitting to distinguish between LØ or LH is by using a noun followed by the Genitive marker =^L. If a noun is LØ, the Genitive floating L links to the preceding toneless segment. If a noun is LH, the final H no longer undergoes downdrift; instead, it surfaces as H, followed by a subsequent tone downstepped due to the Genitive L.

Functional morphemes and pronouns can carry H, L, H ~ H^L, or can be toneless (surfacing with a default M tone), e.g. the Perfective enclitic =*tí* / =*rí*, the Progressive marker *tí*, the non-human third person plural subject pronoun *à*, the presentative marker *á*, the Reciprocal enclitic =*ā* / =*sā*, the Applicative enclitic =*sī* and the Pluractional enclitic =*mī* / =*Vī* / =*lī*. The H tone of morphemes that occur at the beginning of a clause, e.g. the clause-linking marker *mā* and non-future second person singular subject pronouns *mú*, can be optionally realized with M tone, which can be probably explained by the intonation of the beginning of a phrase.

Verb roots can carry H, L and LH, e.g. *yí* / *yíí* ‘beat’,² *zǔǔ* ‘greet’, *tǔǔ* ‘say’, *gǔ* ‘do’, *só* / *sótí* ‘enter’, *ó* / *ókí* / *óó* / *óókí* ‘run’, *māā* / *màá* ‘build’, *vǔǔ* / *vǔǔǔ* ‘write’, *zùrí* ‘be good’.

In most disyllabic verbs, the second syllable is toneless with a default M tone. However, the M tone in some verbs still needs to be checked to determine whether it is a true default M or downdrifted H after L, as in *bèní* ‘dry’. For now, such cases are analyzed as verbs with a toneless second syllable.³

Monosyllabic verbs with a /LH/ tonal melody are phonetically realized with a M tone (e.g. *māā* / *màá* ‘build’), when they are not followed by the Resultative marker =^L. There are also a number of toneless verb roots, e.g. *gǔ* ‘wait’, *kā* / *kālī* ‘see’ and *lǔ* / *lǔlī* ‘be rotten’. However, it is not always clear whether a verb is toneless with a default M tone or if it has an underlying LH pattern, see above.

4.3. Toneless syllables and morae

Toneless syllables and morae are found in nouns, verbs, pronouns and functional morphemes.

In nouns and verbs, they are phonetically realized with a M tone. This M tone can surface on the second mora of a heavy syllable, e.g. *bāā* ‘herd, flock’. An entire syllable can be toneless and surface with M, e.g. *hǔǔ* ‘food’, *wēní* ‘people’, *gǔ* ‘wait’, *kā* / *kālī* ‘see’. Toneless functional morphemes surface with a M tone as well, e.g. the Negative marker *ǔ*, the Predicate final marker =*wā*, and the Reciprocal marker =*ā* / =*sā*, the third person plural pronoun =*rī* in the object and possessive function.

² Variants separated by slashes occur in different morphosyntactic environments, in particular, with different verb-to-verb derivational morphemes and in certain constructions, e.g. in the Applicative construction.

³ The diagnostic context for the presence or absence of /H/ on the second syllable of a verb is the presence of the Resultative marker =^L. For some verbs in my dictionary, this test is yet to be done.

4.4. Tonal phrases

Kugama does not have a tonal phrase.

5. Stress and tone

5.1. Culminativity

Kugama tone is not culminative.

5.2. Stress

Kugama has no stress.

5.3. Positional prominence

In Kugama, a word-initial prosodic prominence is observed in content words (i.e., nouns and verbs). Non-initial syllables of a word form are prosodically weak, as in *kpàmli* ‘learn’ and *gbènē* ‘horse’.

Prosodic prominence is manifested by the restrictions on consonants, vowels, and syllable types. Almost all consonants (except for /ŋ/ and /ʔ/) occur in the onset position of a prominent syllable, while in the non-prominent ones, there are mainly nasals /n/, /ŋ/, /m/, voiceless stops /k/, /p/, /s/, /t/, a lateral /l/, and a tap /ɾ/. Consonants /b/, /β/, /d/, /d̪/, /g/, /kp/, /gb/, /f/, /z/, /v/, /h/, /y/, /w/, /w̃/, /ʔ/ do not occur in the non-prominent position. Any vowel can occur in a prominent syllable, while in a prosodically weak position only short front vowels /i/, /e/, /ɛ/, /a/, /ị/, /ɛ̣/, /ạ/ and, more rarely, short back vowels /ɔ/, /o/, /u/, /ɔ̣/, /ụ/ are found. Long oral and nasal vowels /ii/, /ee/, /εε/, /aa/, /ɔɔ/, /oo/, /uu/, /īī/, /ε̄ε̄/, /āā/, /ɔ̄ɔ̄/, /ūū/ do not occur in prosodically weak position. All syllable types are allowed in the prosodically strong position: V, CV, VV, CVV, VC, and CVC. In the prosodically weak position, only the CV syllables appear.

5.4. Obligatoriness of tone

The presence of a toneme in each word is not obligatory in Kugama. A toneless word surfaces with a M tone on each syllable, e.g. *wēnī* ‘people’.

6. Tonal rules. Segmental rules which have incidence on tones

6.1. Tonal rules

6.1.1. Floating L deletion after L

When a floating L tone occurs after a linked L or after another floating L, it is deleted, see (20) and (21).

- (20) vòòsìrì 'váā
/vòòsì =^L = rí =^L váā/
insect = GEN = POSS = GEN child
'insect of the child'

- (21) dââ 'bâā
/dââ^L =^L bâā/
sheep = GEN herd
'sheep of the herd'

6.1.2. Simplification of H^L sequences

Noun phrases with the demonstrative =*é* and the proximal =*ré* may have two floating L tones: the lexical one of the head noun and the Genitive =^L between these two enclitics. Only the first floating L toneme of these sequences causes downstep, as in (22) and (23). The second floating L toneme, viz. the Genitive =^L, is deleted.

- (22) bí'nááré
/bí^Lná = *é* =^L = *ré*/
granary = DEM = GEN = PROX
'this granary'

- (23) b*é*'*é*rí
/b*é*^L = *é* =^L = rí/
when = DEM = GEN = PROX
'After (dances)...'

6.1.3. H toneme spreading on a toneless mora

H toneme spreads to the right on underlyingly toneless morae if they are followed by a floating L toneme, see (24) and (25).

- (24) ɲáá 'wēm
 /ɲáa =^L wem/
 mouth = GEN person
 'mouth of the person'
- (25) yékí 'váákī
 /yéki =^L váa = ki/
 money = GEN marry = NMLZ
 'bridewealth' (lit. 'money of marrying')

In some instances, when the toneless syllable is followed by floating L, the spreading of the H toneme appears to be optional; as an alternative option, the floating L can be docked onto the toneless syllable, see (26) - (28). The choice of realization is not always clear and may depend on factors such as speech tempo (careful vs. spontaneous) or a position within an utterance (at the beginning vs. the end of an utterance or prepausally vs. non-prepausally). In addition, different realizations may occur with certain lexemes or depend on speaker's preferences. These factors require further clarification.

- (26a) vélí 'ɲᵒᵒkī
 /véli =^L ɲᵒᵒki/
 husband = GEN daughter
 'groom'
- (26b) véli ɲᵒᵒkī
 /véli =^L ɲᵒᵒki/
 husband = GEN daughter
 'groom'
- (27a) váá 'bá 'yēy
 /váa =^L báa =^L yey/
 child = GEN inside = GEN wind
 'bastard'
- (27b) váà bá 'yēy
 /váa =^L báa =^L yey/
 child = GEN inside = GEN wind
 'bastard'

(28a) géré 'dǎéké
 /gére =^L dǎéke^L/
 pig = GEN house
 'domestic pig'

(28b) gérè dǎéké
 /gére =^L dǎéke^L/
 pig = GEN house
 'domestic pig'

6.1.4. H toneme spreading and L toneme delinking

H toneme can also spread across morphological boundaries, viz. before L-toned enclitic: the Presentative marker =è or the Comitative preposition =è. The L toneme of these enclitics can be delinked, as demonstrated in (29) - (32).

(29) máwé 'how' + =è PRST → máwéè ~ máwéé

(30) mós 2SG.NS + =è PRST + =yí QM → mós'yí

(31) ká 'see' + =tí PFV + =è COMM → kátíè ~ kátíé

(32) dǎǎ 'much' + =è PRST → dǎǎé

The H toneme spreading and L toneme delinking is also found with the L-toned non-human third person object pronominal =ǎ. In (33), the H toneme of the Perfective enclitic =tí spreads onto the non-human third person object pronominal =ǎ whose L toneme is delinked. In addition, the hiatus of *i* and *ɔ* is resolved through the deletion of *i*.

(33) ká 'see' + =tí PFV + =ǎ 3NHUM + =wā PFM → kátó'wā

6.1.5. L toneme spreading and H toneme shift

There are cases when the L toneme of the LH melody spreads to the adjacent mora within the same syllable, while the H toneme shifts to the following toneless syllable within the same prosodic word. Compare examples in (34) and (35).

(34) á màá'wā
 /á màá =^L = wa/
 1SG build = RES = PFM
 'I have built'

- (35) á mààkí 'sì
 /á màá = ki = ^L sì/
 1SG build = NMLZ = GEN something
 'I will build something'

6.1.6. Floating L after a toneless mora or syllable

When a floating L tone follows a root with a final toneless segment, it commonly links to that segment, as in (36) - (38). A similar process occurs when a floating L follows monosyllabic LØ nouns, where it links to the preceding toneless segment. In this case, the resulting sequence of LL undergoes fusion, see Section 6.1.7.

- (36) hòḡ sóm̄
 /hḡ = ^L sóm/
 food = GEN guinea_corn
 'dish made of guinea corn'

- (37) wēnì pōkī
 /wēni = ^L pō = ki/
 people = GEN farm = NMLZ
 'farmers'

- (38) dḡḡrì gàá'té
 /dḡḡri = ^L gàá'té/
 star = GEN morning
 'morning star'

After HØ nouns, the floating L can sometimes link to its toneless segment. However, it usually remains unlinked, as the initial H tone spreads from left to right onto the toneless segment, leaving the L tone floating, see Section 6.1.3 for more information.

6.1.7. L tonemes fusion

In monosyllabic LØ nouns, a floating L links to the preceding toneless mora. As a result, the LL sequence fuses into a single L, as shown in (39). This fusion can be supported by the Conformity property of toneme.

- (39) làà dīī
 /làa =^L dīī/
 cheek = GEN fish
 ‘gill’

6.2. Segmental rules affecting tonal density

6.2.1. Resyllabification and tone absorption of H by the following H

When a VC or CVC syllable is followed by an enclitic of the V structure, the entire construction undergoes resyllabification, as seen in (40) and (41), where syllable limits are marked by dots. If the second mora of VC or CVC syllable carries a tone, it can be absorbed by the tone of the following enclitic, as in (42).

- (40) à kè.mē.è
 /à kēm = ε = è/
 1SG tell.VF1 = NMLZ = PRST
 ‘(The story that) I will tell’
- (41) ò.yè léèni ì táákī.è
 /òʸ = è léèni ì táa = ki = è/
 3PL.NHUM = PRST evening IMPS eat.VF3 = NMLZ = PRST
 ‘they (seeds of hibiscus and guinea corn) were the only food to eat’
- (42) kò.mé.‘ré
 /kòm̄ = é = ^L = ré/
 body_hair = DEM = GEN = PROX
 ‘this body hair’

Resyllabification does not occur when two vowels belonging to different morphemes appear together. In example (40), both vowels of the nominalization enclitic = $\bar{\epsilon}$ and the presentative enclitic = $\grave{\epsilon}$ belong to different syllables, as well as in example (41) with the nominalization enclitic = $k\bar{i}$ and the presentative enclitic = $\grave{\epsilon}$.

7. Grammatical tones

Kugama has two tonal morphemes which have a floating L as an exponent. These are the Genitive marker =^L and the Resultative marker =^L.

7.1. Genitive L

The Genitive morpheme is expressed through a floating L tone, which can remain floating or links to a preceding mora according to the rules described in Section 6.1, see (43) - (45).

- (43) vētóŋtó
 /vetóŋ =^L = tó/
 friend = GEN = 1PL.POSS
 ‘our friend’
- (44) dēèrí Zùrí
 /dēe =^L = rí Zùrí^L/
 blood = GEN = POSS Zuri
 ‘blood of Zuri’
- (45) dēèrí ‘wēm
 /dēe =^L = rí =^L wem/
 blood = GEN = POSS = GEN person
 ‘blood of the person’

7.2. Resultative L

In monosyllabic verbs (always represented by heavy syllables), the Resultative marker =^L comes immediately after the root. With H-toned monosyllabic verbs, the Resultative marker can stay afloat surfacing as a downstep of the following tone or link to a preceding mora, as in (46). When it comes after L-toned monosyllabic verbs, the Resultative L is deleted, see (47). The Resultative L remains floating after monosyllabic verbs with a LH tonal melody, as in (48).

- (46) /yíí/ ‘beat (VF3)’ + =^L RES → yíí` or yî
 (47) /gòò/ ‘do (VF3)’ + =^L RES → gòò
 (48) /vèé/ ‘write’ + =^L RES → vèé`

In disyllabic verbs with a L tone on the initial syllable, the Resultative marker =^L docks to the second toneless syllable, as in (49). The Resultative marker =^L occurs twice in a H-toned disyllabic verb: after the first H-toned syllable and the second toneless syllable of a disyllabic verb, as in (50). The Resultative remains floating after the first syllable and links to the second syllable.

- (49) /diimi/ ‘braid (VF4)’ + =^L RES → diimì

(50) /nóomi/ ‘polish’ + =^L RES → nṵ́=^L mī=^L → nṵ́^Lmì

The behavior of fully toneless disyllabic verbs may follow one of two strategies. These verbs either acquire a H tone on their first syllable with the Resultative L or retain a toneless first syllable surfacing with a M tone, as in (51) and (52). Each instance of a toneless verb with Resultative L is analyzed individually, as it is not yet possible to predict which of the two strategies will be employed with a given verb.

(51) /dṵ́ki/ ‘burn (VF4)’ + =^L RES → dṵ́=^L kī=^L → dṵ́^Lkì

(52) /yṵ́mi/ ‘plant’ + =^L RES → yṵ́mì

8. Tonal classes of words

There are no tonal classes in Kugama.

9. Diachrony of tones

10. Tonal notation

Kugama does not have a practical orthography.

11. Annotated text 1

This story was told by Angelina Turuma in the town of Mayo-Belwa (Adamawa State, Nigeria) in April 18, 2018. The recording, transcription, and glossing were carried out by Lora Litvinova.

sì=^L nṵ́a=^L mṵ́ku=é=^L
 [L si] [H nṵ́,a][L =^L] mṵ́,ṵ́.ku[H . = ε][L =^L]
 thing=GEN mouth=GEN river=DEM=GEN

The story (lit. ‘thing of the mouth of the river’)

à kṵ́m = ε = è
 [L a] [L kṵ́,m]. = ε [L . = ε]
 1SG.FUT tell.VF1 = NMLZ = PRST
 I will tell

ɓ̀ɔ̀ ɓ̀àà ɔ̀ = ɛ̀ = ˀ = rɛ̀
 [L ɓ̀ɔ̀] [L ɓ̀a,a] [L ɔ̀][H . = ɛ̀][L = ˀ][H . = rɛ̀]
 3SG.NHUM like 3NHUM = DEM = GEN = PROX

is like this.

à lóɔ̀ˀkòti = ɛ̀ = ˀ lúɔ̀ˀ kà
 [L a] [H lɔ̀,ɔ̀][L ˀ][L .kɔ̀].ti[H . = ɛ̀][L = ˀ] [H lu,ɔ̀][L ˀ] [L ka]
 PRST.COMM time = DEM = GEN before 3.CLM

In old times,

wɛni ɗ́ɔ̀ŋ kòɔ̀ = rí = è
 wɛ.ni [H ɗ́ɔ̀,ŋ] [L kɔ̀,ɔ̀][H . = ri. = ɛ̀][L ˀ]
 people old live.VF3 = PFV = PRST

when elders lived [we were told that]

kà léɛ náa = ri léɛ náa = ri
 [L ka] [H lɛ],ɛ [H na,a]. = ri [H lɛ],ɛ [H na,a]. = ri
 3.CLM rain rain.VF3 = PLAC rain rain.VF3 = PLAC

it was raining heavily.

séɛˀˀ ṭ̣̣pi dàla sòɔ̀sáy
 [H sɛ,ɛ][L ˀ] [H ṭ̣̣][L ,i].pi [L da].la [L sɔ̀,ɔ̀][H .sa,y]
 then darkness outside very

It was very dark outside.

sée we sóðri t̄o = r̄i = è
 [H sɛ,ɛ] we [H .so][L ,o].ri [L to,o][H .ri.ɛ]
 then person female cook = PFV = COM

A woman was cooking

èré n̄ó = ^L zéke
 [L ɛ][H .rɛ] [H n̄o],o[L = ^L] [H zɛ].ke
 PL.3SG.POSS seed = GEN hibiscus

her seeds of hibiscus,

záamàni = é lúy = é = ^L = r̄é
 [H za,a][L .ma].ni[H . = ɛ] [H lu].y[H = ɛ][L = ^L][H . = rɛ]
 time = DEM day = DEM = GEN = PROX

in these [old] times,

à n̄ó = ^L sóm
 [L a] [H n̄o],o[L = ^L] [H so],m
 COM seed = GEN guinea_corn

with seeds of guinea corn.

t̄ò úu^L s̄i = ^L m̄ðki = ɛ nè ǵ kènán fa
 [L t̄o] [H u,u][L ^L] [L si] [L .m̄ð].k = ɛ [L nɛ] ǵ [L kɛ][H .na][L ,n] fa
 INTERJ some something eating there NEG EMPH EMPH

There was no food at all,

ðʸ = è léèni ì táa = ki = è
 [L ɔ][L .y = ε] [H lɛ][L ,ε].ni [L i] [H ta,a]. = ki[L . = ε]
 3PL.NHUM = PRST evening IMPS.FUT eat.VF3 = NMLZ = PRST
 they [seeds of hibiscus and guinea corn] were the only food to eat.

t̀ò séɛ^L ð nóòkì sé í ísi = ð
 [L t̀ɔ] [H sɛ,ɛ][L ^L] [L ɔ] [H nɔ,ɔ][L .ki] [H sɛ] [H i] [H i][L .s = ɔ]
 INTERJ then 3PL.NHUM cook:RES then IMPS pour = 3PL.NHUM
 They [seeds of hibiscus and guinea corn] were cooked and poured [served].

léɛ náa = ri t̀îpi nè s̀òsáy
 [H lɛ],ɛ [H na,a].ri [H t̀i][L ,i].pi [L nɛ] [L sɔ,ɔ][H .sa,y]
 rain rain.VF3 = PLAC darkness there very
 It was raining, and it was very dark.

séé d̀é = è táa = ki = ^L
 [H sɛ,ɛ] [H d̀ɛ][L . = ε] [H ta,a][L . = ki]
 then 3SG.HUM = PROG eat.VF3 = NMLZ = GEN
 She was eating

nóò = ^L zéke = é = ^L = ré
 [H nɔ,ɔ][L = ^L] [H zɛ].kɛ[H . = ε][L = ^L][H . = ré]
 seed = GEN hibiscus = DEM = GEN = PROX
 these seeds of hibiscus.

12. Annotated text 2

This story was told by Jackson Wakili in the town of Mayo-Belwa (Adamawa State, Nigeria) in April 5, 2017. The recording, transcription, and glossing were carried out by Lora Litvinova.

kpáa^L tó gò kpàm=^L déé=^L wàa
 [H kpa,a][L ^L] [H tɔ] [L gɔ] [L kpà],m [H dɛ,ɛ][L =^L] [L wa],a
 how 1PL do.VF1 chief=GEN house=GEN Kugama

How we appoint a [new] Kugama chief,

kpàm véê ɓɓ^L
 [L kpa],m [H vɛ][L ,ɛ] [H ɓɓ][L ^L]
 chief die.VF3:RES when

when a [previous] chief died.

dī sɔ̄mte ɲáa=^L dùrī méé=^L weni dɔ̄ŋ
 [L dī] sɔ̄,m.te [H ɲa,a][L =^L] [L du].ri [H mɛ,ɛ][L =^L] wɛ.ni [H dɔ̄,ŋ]
 3PL.HUM.FUT send:? mouth=GEN clan to=GEN people oldness

They will send clans to elders,

méé=^L weni dɔ̄ŋ
 [H mɛ,ɛ][L =^L] wɛ.ni [H dɔ̄,ŋ]
 to=GEN people oldness

to elders.

dí ε dí hóò véεpi
 [H dí] ε [H dí] [H ho][L ,o] [H vé,ε]pi
 3PL.HUM come 3PL.NHUM bury:RES corpse

Then they bury the corpse.

dí hóò véε 6ó^L
 [H dí] [H ho][L ,o] [H vé,ε] [H 6ó][L ^L]
 3PL.HUM bury:RES corpse when

When they bury the corpse,

dí kèemi = ε = ^L gǎǎ^L hìnkári
 [L dí] [L kε,ε][L .m = ε] [L gǎ][H ,ǎ][L ^L] [L hi,η][H .ka].ri
 3PL.HUM.FUT say.VF4 = NMLZ = GEN other people

they will say to other people

kà kpàm véê wa
 [L ka] [L kpa],m [H vé][L ,ε] wa
 CLM chief die.VF3:RES PFM

that the chief has died.

dí 6ó = si = ε = ^L puy 6áa = ^L bòm
 [L dí] [H 6ó][L . = s = ε] pu,y [H 6a,a][L = ^L] [L bo],m
 3PL.HUM.FUT dig = APPL = NMLZ = GEN hole in = GEN hut

They will dig a hole inside the hut.

6̀̀ dī ɛri = ɛ dī kɛ̀̀ɛmi = ɛ = ^L
 [L 6̀] [L dī] ɛ.r = ɛ [L dī] [L kɛ,ɛ][L .m = ɛ]
 3SG.NHUM 3PL.HUM.FUT come = NMLZ 3PL.HUM.FUT say.VF4 = NMLZ = GEN

They will come and say

a weni = ɛ̀ kà tɛ = í hóo = rí kpàm nè hɛ̀ɛ
 a wɛ.ni[L . = ɛ] [L ka] [H tɛ] [H ho,l] [L kpa],m [L nɛ] [H hɛ̀],ɛ
 ? people = PRST 3.CLM place = IMPS bury = PFV chief there here

to people that it is the place where the chief is buried [inside the hut].

t̀̀ tɛ 6̀^L í hóo = rí kpàm nèk = ɛ ǵ
 [L t̀] tɛ [H 6̀][L ^L] [H i] [H ho,o][H . = ri] [L kpa],m [L nɛ][L .k = ɛ] ǵ
 INTERJ place chief IMPS bury = PFV chief there = PRST NEG

It is not the place where they buried the chief

6̀áa = ^L ð = ɛ̀ = ^L = rɛ̀
 [H 6̀a,a][L = ^L] [H ɔ][L = ^L][H . = rɛ̀]
 inside = GEN 3PL.NHUM = DEM = GEN = PROX

inside this one.

ɛ̀ɛ í nàkí lúy dī 6̀ɛɛ tɛ
 [L ɛ,ɛ] [H i] [L na][H .ki] [H lu],y [H dī] [L 6̀ɛ,ɛ] tɛ
 INTERJ IMPS choose.VF2 day 3PL.HUM call:RES someone

They choose a day, they call people

dǐ eri ì gǝ̀ = ki = ^L kpàm
 [H dǐ] ε.ri [L i] [L gǝ̀][L .ki] [L kpa],m
 3PL.HUM come IMPS.FUT do.VF1 = NMLZ = GEN chief
 to come to appoint a chief.

wem = é = ^L dǐ eri = ε = ^L gǝ̀ = ki = ^L kpàm
 we[H .m = ε][L = ^L] [L dǐ] ε[L .r = ε] [L gǝ̀][L .ki] [L kpa],m
 person = DEM = GEN 3PL.HUM.FUT come = NMLZ = 3PL.HUM do.VF1 = NMLZ = GEN chief
 The person that they will appoint as a chief...

kpàm = é = ^L gǝ̀ = ki = ^L = ré lúð vé = tí
 [L kpa][H .m = ε][L = ^L] [L gǝ̀][H . = ki][L = ^L][H . = ré] [H lu][L ,ð] [H vé][H . = tí]
 chief = DEM = GEN do.VF1:RES = NMLZ = RES = 3SG.HUM before die.VF1 = PFV
 The chief who was before and died,

dǐ séli = ^L = ti súm = ré wa
 [H dǐ] [H sé][L ,l][H . = li] [H su],m[H .ré] wa
 3PL.HUM cut.VF2 = RES = PFV hair = 3SG.HUM = POSS PFM
 they cut his hair.

dǐ eri = ε = ì ɓó = ki = ^L
 [L dǐ] ε[L .r = ε] [H ɓó][L . = ki]
 3PL.HUM.FUT come = NMLZ = IMPS give = NMLZ = GEN
 They will come they will give

kpàm = é =^L = ré 6̀̀ náa =^L
 [L kpa][H .m = é][L = L][H = ré] [L 6̀̀] [H na][L ,a]
 chief = DEM = GEN = PROX 3SG.NHUM hand = DEF?

it into *this chief's* hands.

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List of abbreviations and symbols

= enclitic

~ free variation

/ conditioned allomorphs

APPL applicative

COM comitative

COMM common noun

CLM clause linking marker

DEF definite

DEM demonstrative

EMPH emphasis

FUT future

GEN genitive

H high tone
HUM human
IMPS impersonal pronoun
INTERJ interjection
L low tone
M mid-tone
NEG negation
NHUM non-human
NMLZ nominalization
PFM predicate-final marker
PFV perfective
PL plural
PLAC pluractional
POSS possessive
PROG progressive
PROX proximal demonstrative
PRST presentative
RECP reciprocal
RES resultative
SG singular
TBU tone-bearing unit
VEN ventive
VF1 Verb Form 1
VF2 Verb Form 2
VF3 Verb Form 3
VF4 Verb Form 4